

A Study on Impact of Information Technology in Hrm

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Abstract

HR management practices are important part of an organization's strategy and human capital may be viewed as its most important asset. As it may also represent one of its largest costs in terms of recruitment, compensation and training, it is understandable that it must control those costs effectively. The contemporary HR function in both public and private sector organizations face various challenges in how and to whom it delivers its services, as well as criticism of its effectiveness both strategically and financially. In the recent era for hnological up gradation and implementation for various activities, IT is playing very important and crucial part in all the organizations. Today, even the situation is like many businesses cannot function without the use of computer technology. This impact is seen nearly in all areas of business like finance, accounting, human resources, marketing, operations, purchase etc. Technology continues to have a significant impact on HR practices. Various HR practices like HR planning, Recruitment and selection, Training and development, Payroll and Performance Management by use of technology. Use of technology has positive as well as negative impact on human resources.

Keywords:- -_Information Technology, HR Management, HR Information System.

Introduction: -

Human Resource Management:-

HRM has a variety of definitions, but there is general agreement that it has a closer fit with business strategy than previous models, specifically, personnel management. De Cenzo and Stephens (1996) defined HRM as the part of the organisation that is concerned with the people dimension, and it is normally a staff or support function in the organisation.

Information Technology in HRM:-

The function of the Human Resources Management department is generally administrative and common to almost all organisations. It is mainly to reduce the manual workload of these The introduction and implementation of information technology within the human resource department of organisations is a complex matter and that the requirements for such introduction and implementation differs from firm to firm depending on the nature of the firm's human resource management strategies. The use of ICT (Information and Communications Technology) can establish The introduction of information technology to human resource management activities is usually driven by potential factors such as the speed and efficiency of processes, cost savings, enhanced customer satisfaction, accuracy of data, improved transparency and consistency of processes, increased availability of information and the facilitation of a change in the role of HR managers. The major areas of implementation of human resource management system include payroll, work time, benefits administration, HR information management, and recruiting, training system and performance record (Adewoye & Obasan, 2012).

administrative activities, organisations began to automate many of these processes by introducing IT-oriented software applications which gradually led to the development of specialized Human Resource Management Systems (HRMS). The use of information technology in HRM has grown considerably in recent years and there are now extensive applications across a wide range of HRM activities in all the sectors. HRMS is a system that helps an organisation to acquire, store, manipulate, analyse, retrieve and distribute information about an organisation's human resources. The term 'e-HRM' is used to express the use of information technology within the HRM function.

more virtual customer relationships within the organisation and can also improve employee voice through social networking (Martin et al, 2009). Wachira (2010) observed that HRM should be concerned with application of internet and web based systems and mobile technologies to change the nature of interactions among HR staff.

Model for effectiveness of HRM

Review of Literature: -

Nzari (2017) Information technology plays an important role in increasing the efficiency and productivity of human resources and in general in the growth of organizations. Because human resources are the main capital and strategic factor of any organization. On the other hand, today, having high quality human resources with high productivity, having new and up-to-date information and methods and information technology skills, determines the position of nations in the hierarchy of global divisions. When human resource training is objectively aimed at the excellence and growth of organizations.

Tanya Bondarouka & Chris Brewster (2015) learning from running an HRM course at Harvard and offered what is frequently called the Harvard map of the territory a view of HRM as being moulded by its different contexts, defined (sometimes differently) by its varied stakeholders, and having long-term outcomes that impact all of the potential stakeholders. In information technology (hereinafter referred to as technology) we start from observations that technologies have changed (through enabling and/or constraining). HRM practices by introducing for example, e-recruitment, e-training, or e-competence management.

Imran Rana, Ijaz Mirza & Sajid Muhamaad (2014) this research paper is about recruitment, selection and training procedure in a Rescue 1122. It comes with findings like the policy should non-discriminatory, fair & should meet all legislative requirements. In selection process, no personal information should be revealed to selection panel. This company mostly using external recruitment. It comes with findings like management use training need assessment and also go for capacity building. The company should appoint professionally HR qualified people which will help to minimize flaws.

Neeraj Kumari (2012) The main objective of this research paper is to identify general practices that organizations use to recruit and select employees and, to determine how the recruitment and selection practices affect organizational outcomes at SMC Global Securities Ltd. The research methodology applied is the exploratory. This paper came with findings like, company considered portals as the most important medium of hiring employees. The employees working in the company consider the employee references are one of the most reliable source of hiring the new employees. Company always takes in consideration the cost-benefit ratio. Human Resources Information Systems (HRIS) are systems used to collect, record, store, analyse and

retrieve data concerning an organization's human resources, but it is not merely reduction of administrative procedures. The importance of HRIS system is multifaceted, ranging from operational assistance in collecting, storing and preparing data for reports, simplifying and accelerating the processes and controlling the available data, reducing labour costs for HR departments, and providing timely and diverse information to the management of the company, based on which it is possible to make quality strategic decisions related to human capital.

Objectives Of The Study:-

1. To identify different organisational variables in Indian companies while adapting HRIS, experiencing its impact to give a better HR output.
2. To identify different HR areas where organisations are prone to use Human Resource Information Systems.

Hypotheses Of The Study:-

H01: Type of business sector, Company ownership and Company origin do not have a significant effect on the adaption of information technology in HRM in the form of HRIS.

H02: Type of business sector, Company ownership and Company origin do not have significant effects on impact of HRIS.

Research Methodology:-

Primary data are procured in this research. The primary data is collected through a well-structured survey instrument that is distributed among the select Indian organizations that are selected using purposive sampling method. Quantitative Research is used to quantify the problem through generating numerical data that can be transformed into useable statistics. In this study, quantitative research design is found to be the most suitable type of research design. The population for this study includes HR managers and HR staff who are directly responsible and are involved in HR activities in their respective organizations and also other staff from other departments who are indirectly involved in HRM activities in their respective companies due to their supportive job roles. The sample subjects for the present research are the select Indian industries from different business sectors.

For the purpose of the present study, a list of wide range of companies is procured from the sources such as Confederation of Indian Industry and other websites. The companies are selected based on purposive sampling method. A well-structured questionnaire is prepared and administered to a total of 75 respondents.

Analysis And Interpretation:-

Table No. 01 Type Of Business And Adaption Of It In Hrm

S.No.	Activities	Type of business	N	Mean	S.D	t value	p value
1	HR planning	Manufacturing	45	16.31	1.47	1.3749	0.1734
		Service	30	15.84	1.42		
2	Recruitment and selection	Manufacturing	45	9.25	1.09	0.9581	0.3412
		Service	30	9.49	1.02		
3	Training and Development	Manufacturing	45	10.42	1.52	0.6928	0.4906
		Service	30	10.18	1.39		
4	Payroll	Manufacturing	45	7.59	1.28	0.5143	0.6086
		Service	30	7.44	1.17		
5	Performance Management	Manufacturing	45	12.68	1.33	0.7420	0.4605
		Service	30	12.46	1.14		

It is proved that there is no significant difference between manufacturing and service sectors among their adaption of Information technology in HRM in the form of HRIS. Hence, the null hypothesis of

type of sector is accepted for 'HR Planning', 'Selection and recruitment', 'Training and development', 'Payroll', and 'Performance Management'.

Table No. 02 Company Ownership And Adaption Of It

S.No.	Activities	Ownership	N	Mean	S.D	t value	p value
1	HR planning	Public	25	17.85	1.89	4.5600	0.0001
		Private	50	16.24	1.16		
2	Recruitment and selection	Public	25	14.32	1.48	3.7173	0.0004
		Private	50	13.08	1.30		
3	Training and Development	Public	25	15.58	1.66	4.2910	0.0001
		Private	50	14.02	1.39		
4	Payroll	Public	25	12.77	1.17	4.1193	0.0001
		Private	50	11.35	1.51		
5	Performance Management	Public	25	8.55	1.41	3.3865	0.0001
		Private	50	7.22	1.69		

It is proved that there is significant difference between the respondents from public and private sectors among their adaption of IT into HRM

activities. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected for 'HR planning', 'Selection and Recruitment', 'Training and Development', 'Payroll', and 'Performance Management'.

Table No. 03 Company Origin And Adaption Of It

S.No.	Activities	Origin	N	Mean	S.D	t value	p value
1	HR planning	Indian	60	18.33	1.40	3.4962	0.0008
		MNC	15	16.95	1.22		
2	Recruitment and selection	Indian	60	13.89	1.79	3.3949	0.0011
		MNC	15	12.18	1.54		
3	Training and Development	Indian	60	11.77	1.37	4.4267	0.0001
		MNC	15	10.08	1.10		
4	Payroll	Indian	60	17.62	1.49	3.0904	0.0028
		MNC	15	16.32	1.31		
5	Performance Management	Indian	60	14.44	1.89	2.8121	0.0063
		MNC	15	12.88	2.05		

It is proved that there is significant difference between the origin of companies and their adaption of IT in 'HR Planning', 'Selection and Recruitment', 'Training and Development',

'Payroll', and 'Performance Management'. Hence, null hypothesis of company origin is rejected for all the variables.

Table No. 04 Type of Business And Impact Of Hris

S.No.	Impact	Type of business	N	Mean	S.D	t value	p value
1	Reduced Time Consumption	Manufacturing	45	9.74	1.40	0.3688	0.7133
		Service	30	9.62	1.35		
2	Information Flow	Manufacturing	45	11.25	1.08	0.1209	0.9041
		Service	30	11.22	1.01		
3	Decision Making	Manufacturing	45	16.84	0.96	0.5913	0.5562
		Service	30	16.71	0.89		
4	Cost Aspect	Manufacturing	45	13.93	1.73	0.1998	0.8422
		Service	30	13.85	1.65		

It is proved that there is no significant difference between manufacturing or service sectors for the Impact of HRIS. Hence, null hypothesis of type of

business is accepted for 'Reduced Time Consumption', 'Information Flow', 'Decision Making', and 'Cost Aspect'.

Table No. 05 Company Ownership And Impact Of Hris

S.No.	Impact	Ownership	N	Mean	S.D	t value	p value
1	Reduced Time Consumption	Public	25	15.59	1.84	0.5354	0.5940
		Private	50	15.36	1.71		
2	Information Flow	Public	25	12.42	1.06	0.9239	0.3586
		Private	50	12.16	1.19		

3	Decision Making	Public	25	17.49	1.33	0.9188	0.3612
		Private	50	17.18	1.40		
4	Cost Aspect	Public	25	14.22	1.91	0.5277	0.5993
		Private	50	13.98	1.83		

It is proved that there is no significant difference between the respondents' reported company ownership on the Impact of HRIS variables of

'Reduced Time Consumption', 'Information Flow', 'Decision Making' and 'Cost Aspect'. Hence, the null hypothesis is approved for Impact of HRIS.

Table No. 06 Company Origin And Impact Of Hris

S.No.	Impact	Origin	N	Mean	S.D	t value	p value
1	Reduced Time Consumption	Indian	60	9.97	1.65	0.4315	0.6674
		MNC	15	9.76	1.83		
2	Information Flow	Indian	60	12.40	1.58	0.4758	0.6356
		MNC	15	12.62	1.69		
3	Decision Making	Indian	60	17.28	1.21	0.7372	0.4634
		MNC	15	17.02	1.27		
4	Cost Aspect	Indian	60	13.19	1.14	1.0160	0.3130
		MNC	15	12.86	1.06		

It is proved that there is no significant difference between company origin and the Impact of HRIS variables, 'Reduced Time Consumption', 'Information Flow', 'Decision Making', and 'Cost Aspect'. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted for all the Impact of HRIS variables.

Findings:-

- 1 Adaption of IT in HRM in Form of HRIS:**
 This research shows that different business units in terms of nature of their output, i.e. manufacturing and service sectors have no significant effect on their adaptation of information technology in their human resource management in form of HRIS. There exists a significant effect of company ownership, i.e. public and private sector on the adaptation of information technology in form of HRIS. With respect to the origin of companies, there found to be a significant effect of company origin on their adaptation of HRIS.
- 2. Impact of HRIS:** The research also indicated that Impact of HRIS is perceived uniformly by both the manufacturing and service sectors. It was found that the employees from both business units exhibited their opinions about Impact of HRIS in terms of reduced time consumption, easy information flow, better

decision making and reduced costs. Similarly, with respect to company ownership there is no significant difference between the perceptions of respondents from public and private sector companies. Same finding is also observed in case of company origin. Respondents both from MNCs and firms of Indian origin exhibited similar pattern of impact of HRIS in terms of reduced time, clear information flow, proper decision making and reduced costs.

Limitations of The Study:-

- The findings are primarily based on the data collected through a questionnaire from key informants. Gathering the data in their own words might have thrown up some light on what actually is going on regarding HRIS in their HRM activities.
- This research is primarily based on primary information, i.e., opinion survey. One of the major problems with this type of study is that the findings do not reveal what organizations are actually doing. The information disclosed by the respondents may not be the true reflection of actual HRIS modules followed by them. Hence, the limitation of this study is that over-reporting or under-reporting of such activities may

produce biased results. A more qualitative research with case studies is necessary.

3. The effectiveness of the research methodology used influence the validity of the findings. The aim of the study is to cover the Indian industries, but the sample size is 226 which may not be proportionate to represent the whole country though the sample is adequate as explained in the research methodology. The findings in this paper are based on information of only a limited number of organizations and hence cannot be generalized.

Conclusion:-

1. Information technology has penetrated in to every kind of business, promoting their efficiency and effectiveness. Human Resource Information Systems, as an application of information technology, abolishes the traditional Human Resources Management introducing information systems and the use of computer. HRIS can be stated as intersection of human resources and information technology. Some companies successfully implement HRIS in all areas of HRM while others apply HRIS in few areas. There could be several reasons for this restriction. Perception of employees may be considered as one major factor for such.
2. This study is based on the premise that just a survey of HRIS initiatives in Indian companies is not sufficient. There is a need for developing and testing a model which could be used for effective implementation of HRIS leading to effectiveness of HRM.
3. The results pertaining to the adaptation of information technology in form of HRIS are analysed in relation to type of business sector, company ownership and company origin.
4. This research reveals that there is no significant difference between the respondents from manufacturing and service sector units while adapting HRIS in their firms.
5. The research also indicates that there is significant difference in the respondents from public and private sector units about the adaption of HRIS. Similarly, there is significant difference among the MNCs and companies of Indian origin about the adaptation of HRIS.

References: -

1. **Nzari, Q.R. (2017).** Electronic Human Resource Management. Tehran: Shalok publication.
2. **Bharti, P. & Kapila, M. (2014).** Impact of IT on Human Resource Management: A Study of Selected Indian Banks. Retrieved from SSRN
3. **Imran Rana , Ijaz Mirza & Sajid Muhamaad (2014) “ Study of Effectiveness on Recruitment & Selection process of RESCUE 1122”**

International Journal of Research in Social Science.

4. **Banerji, S.C.(2013).** A Study of Issues & Challenges of Implementation of Information Technology in HRM. Global Journal of Management and Business Studies,3(4), 435-440.SSN(2249-2496), Vol.4,Issue 1,pp 339-347, February 2014.
5. **Kamal & Kumar, A. (2013).** Impact of Technology Advancement on Human Resource Performance. International Journal on Arts, Management and Humanitie,2(2), 43-47.
6. **Neeraj Kumari (2012) “ A Study of the Recruitment and Selection process: SMC Global “Industrial Engineering Letters ISSN 2224-6096 (print) ISSN 2225-0581 (online) Vol 2, No.1.**